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Influence of Phosphorus Fertilizers Application on Phosphorus use Efficiency and Grain Protein of Winter Wheat in Alkaline-Calcareous Soil, Southern Algeria

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ABSTRACT

Three field experiments (2008 to 2011) were conducted to evaluate the ability of winter wheat (*Triticum durum* Desf. var. Carioca) to utilize and acquire soil phosphorus and nitrogen under different sources of phosphate fertilizers (Fosfactyl, Single super phosphate and Mono-ammonium-phosphate) and rates of applications (30, 60, 90 and 120 kg Pha⁻¹) with a fixed level of nitrogen fertilization. Results revealed a significant effect of P rates on phosphorus use efficiency (PUE) and nitrogen use efficiency (NUE); however, P sources fertilizer had non-significant effect in all three cropping seasons. PUE and NUE decreased markedly with increasing P supply that did not result in an improvement of P and N uptake. Grain protein content was significantly influenced by phosphorus fertilization in 2008-09. The best values were obtained by Single super phosphate and P rate 60 kg ha⁻¹.

Key words: Arid area, Durum wheat, Grain protein, NUE, Phosphorus fertilization, PUE.

INTRODUCTION

Low soil phosphorus availability is a primary constraint for plant growth in many terrestrial ecosystems, as P is involved in several energy transformation and biochemical reactions of plant growth and development (Liao *et al.*, 2008). Mineral fertilization, especially that of P significantly increased wheat grain yield and protein content (Gaj *et al.*, 2013). Most of P accumulation by wheat occurs during pre-anthesis and consequently adequate P uptake during early vegetative stages that is critical for grain production (Grant *et al.*, 2001). However, large amounts of P fertilizers are generally required for sustainable crop production, which can entails risks of environmental pollution (Liang *et al.*, 2015), by phosphorus accumulation in the soil, which also increases the risk of aquatic eutrophication (White and Brown, 2010; Xu *et al.*, 2014).

In relation to nitrogen and potassium, recovery of P fertilizers by crop plants is usually very low due to high capacity of soil to fix P (Manske *et al.*, 2001; Lynch, 2007). High calcium carbonate contents, high pH, sandy texture and low organic matter coupled with low rainfall are the principal factors for low P availability in dry land of Southeastern of Algeria; consequently, phosphorus fertilizer efficiency remains low (Delgado *et al.*, 2002; Al Harbi *et al.*, 2013). The climatic factors such as high temperature can have a significant effect in reducing yield and quality of wheat and drought stress limits photosynthetic production because of stomatal closure (Li *et al.*, 2000; Altenbach *et al.*, 2003).

Nutrient utilization efficiency has long been concerned with several plant-related factors, in particular, rooting (density and length) (Sandana and Pinochet, 2014), mycorrhizal colonization (Li *et al.*, 2006; Djadjaglo and Richter, 2008), root exudates (Dakora and Philips, 2002)

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and chemical forms of P in soil (Liao *et al.*, 2008). In addition, P deficiency is often associated with changes in root morphology which induce changes in root functions that also increase PUE (Liao *et al.*, 2008). For example in some species the release of protons, organic-acid anions, phosphatases and other compounds into the rhizosphere (Vance *et al.*, 2003) can help release P from the fixed pools in the soil. However, increase in soil P level reduced the length of root hairs (Gahoonia *et al.*, 1999).

Use of phosphorus fertilizers had a beneficial effect on phosphorus use efficiency (Ghafoor, 2016). However, the choice of phosphorus fertilizer type is essential because the reaction of added P after dissolution decides its availability to the crop growth and fertilizer use efficiency (Sushanta *et al.*, 2014).

The management of phosphate fertilization is complex because of the various phosphorus transformations that occur in the soil-plant system, reducing the efficiency of fertilization and the productivity of durum wheat (Marshner, 1995; Liao *et al.*, 2008).

In order to improve the productivity of cereals in general and wheat in particular, we studied the effects of different phosphate sources fertilizers and rates on phosphorus use efficiency of wheat crop in arid area conditions of southeastern Algeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Field trials

The research was performed in three different growing seasons (2008-09, 2009-10 and 2010-11) in El-Menia (southeastern Algeria, 30°57 N, 2°78 E, 397 m above sea level). The region is characterized by an arid climate, with very low and erratic rainfall (<100 mm) and warm dry summers with maximum air temperature exceeding 40°C. During the three cropping seasons, the maximum temperature average ranged between 25-35°C from February to May (Fig 1).

The main soil characteristics of the three plots of the same site used for experimental trials are presented in Table 1. Plots were laid out in hierarchical two-factor model design with three P source fertilizers applied at sowing time at four rates for the first season (30, 60, 90 and 120 kg P/ha) and at three rates during second and third growing seasons (30, 60 and 90 kg P/ha). The P fertilizer tested in 2008-09 were Single Super Phosphate P 20 and Fosfactyl P 22, while, the third fertilizer, Mono-ammonium phosphate NP 12:52, was added in 2009-10 and 2010-11. Crop was irrigated with center pivot system and receives an amount of 750 mm water during its growth cycle. Water is pumped from the continental interlayer at 250 m deep and had a good quality with low salinity sodicity risks. For each treatment, plants were sown in 1800 m² plots (24x75 m). The seedling rate was 200 kg/ha. The plots were fertilized with 212 kg N/ha as ammonium nitrate and urea (UAN 32), split into several provisions applied through fertigation.

Sampling and plant measurement

At harvest, seed samples were collected for chemical analysis of phosphorus and nitrogen. Phosphorus use efficiency (PUE) and their components were defined

Fig 1: Evolution of Tmax by year.

Table 1: Physical and chemical properties of soil.

Parameters	Units	2008/2009	2009/2010	2010/2011
Textural class		Sandy	Sandy	Sandy
Sand	g kg ⁻¹	99.1	98	93.3
Silt+Clay	g kg ⁻¹	0.9	2.3	6.7
Soil reaction (pH) (1:5 soil water extract)		8.44	8.62	8.6
EC (1:5 soil water extract)	dSm ⁻¹	0.171	0.175	0.114
Lime content	%	8.93	13.5	1.84
Active lime	%	8.286	7.21	-
Organic matter ¶	%	0.106	0.12	0.6
Total nitrogen †	%	0.087	0.065	0.01
Available P ‡	mg kg ⁻¹	2.261	4.12	45.66

¶ Walkley-Black method.

† Kjeldahl method.

‡ Olsen method.

analogue to the definition of nitrogen use efficiency by Moll *et al.* (1982). Use efficiency of P or N was defined as grain weight Gw (kg ha⁻¹) per unit of available element (kg ha⁻¹) in the soil and expressed as absorption efficiency and the utilization efficiency. The Absorption efficiency (PAE, NAE)

was calculated as P or N uptake (kg ha⁻¹) per P or N available in soil (kg ha⁻¹) and Utilization efficiency (PUTE, NUTE) was calculated as grain weight (kg ha⁻¹) per P or N uptake (kg ha⁻¹). Grain protein content was determined by kjeldahl nitrogen multiplied by 5.7.

Table 2: Effect of different sources and phosphorus rates application on PUE, PAE and PUTE of grains wheat.

Year	PUE kgG/kgPav	PAE KgPupt/kgPav	PUTE KgG/kgPupt	NUE kgG/kgNav	NAE KgNupt/kgNav	NUTE KgG/kgNupt	Prot. (%)
2008/2009							
<i>Fertilizers</i>							
SSP	179.9	0.915	136.6	32.27	0.786	43.56 ^b	13.33 ^a
Fosfactyl	206.3	1.505	138.5	35.41	0.820	45.98 ^a	12.48 ^b
	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	*	*
LSD (5%)	-	-	-	-	-	2.348	0.86
<i>Levels (kg ha⁻¹)</i>							
30	290.0 ^a	2.082 ^a	140.3	29.71	0.638	44.08 ^b	12.97 ^b
60	209.8 ^b	1.517 ^b	141.1	34.97	0.948	39.71 ^c	14.56 ^a
90	153.3 ^c	1.195 ^c	129.1	35.47	0.753	51.10 ^a	11.16 ^c
120	119.1 ^d	0.865 ^d	139.7	35.2	0.870	44.19 ^b	12.91 ^b
	***	***	ns	ns	ns	***	**
LSD (5%)	29.08	0.25	-	-	-	3.033	0.528
General means	193.04	1.210	137.6	33.84	0.802	44.77	12.90
2009/2010							
<i>Fertilizers</i>							
SSP	182.13	0.697	260.5	30.73	0.954	32.21	17.7
Fosfactyl	172.60	0.673	259.1	28.36	0.877	32.66	17.53
MAP	188.76	0.719	256.8	31.17	0.970	32.13	17.58
	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
<i>Levels(kg ha⁻¹)</i>							
30	250.5 ^a	0.955 ^a	263.03 ^a	30.72 ^a	0.951	32.31	17.58
60	174.7 ^b	0.674 ^b	256.30 ^b	31.07 ^a	0.977	32.01	17.59
90	118.4 ^c	0.461 ^c	257.10 ^b	28.41 ^b	0.873	32.66	17.63
	***	***	*	*	ns	ns	ns
LSD (5%)	17.71	0.067	6.71	2.725	-	-	-
General means	181.2	0.696	258.8	30.07	0.934	32.33	17.60
2010/2011							
<i>Fertilizers</i>							
SSP	29.41	0.18	169.2	34.80	0.613	61.25	10.07
Fosfactyl	28.96	0.174	173.7	31.66	0.631	53.12	10.83
MAP	32.54	0.221	183.2	32.17	0.579	56.41	9.90
	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Levels (kg ha⁻¹)</i>							
30	30.84 ^{ab}	0.242 ^a	144.5 ^b	31.31 ^b	0.612 ^a	53.87	10.71
60	33.24 ^a	0.174 ^b	194.8 ^a	35.93 ^a	0.607 ^{ab}	60.26	9.72
90	26.84 ^b	0.16 ^b	186.8 ^{ab}	31.40 ^b	0.604 ^b	56.65	10.37
	**	***	**	*	*	ns	ns
LSD (5%)	5.049	0.046	44.94	4.057	0.004	-	-
General means	30.31	0.192	175.4	32.88	0.607	56.93	10.27

*, **, *** Significant at $P \leq 0.05$, $P \leq 0.01$ and $P \leq 0.001$, respectively, ns: Not significant, different superscript letters in a column shows significant difference. PUE: phosphorus use efficiency; PAE: Phosphorus absorption efficiency; PUTE: phosphorus utilization efficiency; NUE: nitrogen use efficiency; NAE: nitrogen absorption efficiency; NUTE: nitrogen utilization efficiency.

Statistical analysis

Experimental data were recorded and classified using Microsoft Office Excel 2010. The significance between the means was determined using analysis of variance (ANOVA) at the level $P \leq 0.05$ with the software package Statistica 8.0.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phosphorus and nitrogen use efficiency

Data in Table 2 showed that the phosphorus use efficiency (PUE) is strongly affected by phosphorus rates ($P \leq 0.001$), while they were not affected by phosphorus sources in all experiments. The highest mean PUE was obtained in the

year 2008-09, which was twice and six times higher than that of 2009-10 and 2010-11, consequently.

Increased phosphorus supply had a highly significant negative effect on the PUE regardless of the year, more so during last two growing seasons (2009-10 and 2010-11) for NUE ($P \leq 0.05$) and the P levels 30 and 60 gave the best values (Table 2, Fig 2).

These results are identical to the observations by Sandana and Pinochet (2014), Balcha (2014) and Ghafoor (2016). They also reported that P sources had non-significant effect and the lower phosphorus use efficiency was observed at higher P application rates. In the case of nitrogen fertilization, Mandic *et al.* (2015), Zemichael *et al.* (2017)

Fig 2: Effect of phosphorus fertilization on PUE and NUE variation.

Table 3: Correlations between wheat grain protein content and P, N use efficiency and their components.

	PUE	PAE	PUTE	NUE	NAE	NUTE
2008-09	0.247 ^{ns}	0.188 ^{ns}	0.253 ^{ns}	0.027 ^{ns}	0.554 ^{**}	-0.980 ^{***}
2009-10	-0.039 ^{ns}	-0.015 ^{ns}	-0.114 ^{ns}	0.097 ^{ns}	0.272 [*]	-0.288 [*]
2010-11	0.155 ^{ns}	0.483 ^{***}	-0.350 [*]	0.134 ^{ns}	0.662 ^{***}	-0.825 ^{***}

*, **, *** Significant at $P \leq 0.05$, $P \leq 0.01$ and $P \leq 0.001$, respectively, ns: Not significant, different superscript letters in a column shows significant difference. PUE: phosphorus use efficiency; PAE: Phosphorus absorption efficiency; PUTE: phosphorus utilization efficiency; NUE: nitrogen use efficiency; NAE: nitrogen absorption efficiency; NUTE: nitrogen utilization efficiency.

and Pandey *et al.* (2018) also reported that increased N level reduced NUE.

Phosphorus and nitrogen absorption efficiency

The efficiency of absorption reflects the ability of plant to extract phosphorus or nitrogen from the soil. PAE is strongly affected by phosphorus rates in the three experiments (Table 2). Differences between treatments are very highly significant ($P \leq 0.001$), while fertilizer source had non-significant effect on PAE.

For all tests, the rate 30 kg ha⁻¹ soil supply had the best phosphorus absorption efficiency, whereas the highest rate gave the lowest PAE values. This efficiency was reduced due to increasing phosphorus inputs that did not result in an improvement of P uptake. In 2008-09, the PAE was twice as high as in 2009-10 and eight times higher than in 2010-11. This can be explained by high temperatures, above 30°C, occurred during anthesis for 2008-09 and during grain filling for 2009-10 and 2010-11; consequently the dry matter accumulation in grain was interrupted and grain weight decreased (Hunt *et al.*, 1991; Wu *et al.*, 2018; Erekul and Yigit, 2018). P uptake into shoots increased substantially with increased P supply as a result of increased dry weight and increased shoot P concentration (Osborne and Rengel, 2002).

Nitrogen absorption efficiency was influenced by P rates only in 2010-11. The lowest P level 30 kg ha⁻¹ recorded the best value, following by the two levels 60 kg ha⁻¹ and 90 kg ha⁻¹ respectively. Pierozan *et al.* (2015), in their study on nitrogen fertilization of soybean found that NUE was dependent on the phenological stage of the crop and climate conditions during crop growth, in addition to the timing of fertilizer application.

Phosphorus and nitrogen utilization efficiency

It expressed the efficiency with which the phosphorus absorbed is utilized to produce grain (Moll *et al.*, 1982). In 2009-10 and 2010-11, significant results were obtained for P rates on PUTE, however, source of fertilizer had non-significant effect. The best values were obtained by the level 30 kg P/ha in 2009-10 and the 60 kg P/ha rate in 2010-11 (Table 2). The results were in confirmation with the findings of Osborne and Rengel (2002) and Fernández *et al.* (2009), who concluded that phosphorus utilization efficiency decreased markedly with increasing P supply for all cereals studied.

NUTE was significantly affected by P fertilizers ($P \leq 0.05$) and rates ($P \leq 0.001$) in 2008-09, where fertilizer fosfactyl and P level 90 kg ha⁻¹ gave the best results (Table 2).

Grain protein

The total protein content of durum wheat is a quality factor closely related to the grain nitrogen concentration. They vary under the influence of genetic as well as agro-climatic factors (Triboi *et al.*, 2000). It resulted from a balance within the plant, between nitrogen nutrition and carbon nutrition (Jeuffroy and Oury, 2012).

In the present study, grain protein content was significantly influenced by source P fertilizer ($P \leq 0.05$) and P rates ($P \leq 0.01$) in the first growing season 2008-09, where SSP and 60 kg ha⁻¹ recorded the best values (Table 2). These results confirmed the findings of Zhu *et al.* (2012) and Zhang *et al.* (2017) who indicated that the increasing in P application decreased grain protein content of wheat. The optimum P fertilizer increased grain yield and improved grain quality with high P use efficiency, which improved leaf area index, increased chlorophyll content and photosynthetic rate, stable acid phosphatase activity to accumulate more dry matter after anthesis (Zhu *et al.*, 2012).

The correlations achieved between different parameters studied (Table 3) revealed that grain protein content was related positively to NAE and negatively to NUTE in the three seasons. While a positive relationship was established between protein content and PAE only in 2010-11. According to Crista *et al.* (2012), Phosphorus has no big influence like nitrogen on protein content, it supports in better assimilation and metabolism of nitrogen forms. Paunescu *et al.* (2009) indicated that environmental factors significantly influenced wheat grain yield and protein accumulation in grain, particularly affecting the quantity and quality of gluten. Dryness or high temperatures during grain filling induced a decrease in the protein and gluten content of grains (Daniel and Triboi, 2000). It also affects more carbonaceous nutrition than nitrogen, therefore, tending to increase protein content (Labuschagne *et al.*, 2009; Jeuffroy and Oury, 2012; Šukalovic *et al.*, 2013). These findings were in perfect agreement with our results obtained in 2009-10, where the T_{max} during grain filling exceeded 30°C, resulting average protein content upper 17.6%.

CONCLUSION

Through the investigative study of the effect of phosphorus fertilizers application on phosphorus use efficiency in durum wheat, we conclude that the best results are recorded by Single super phosphate fertilizer and at an optimum P rate, 60 kg ha⁻¹, in Southeastern Algeria conditions.

The mechanisms of nutrients efficiency in general and phosphorus in particular will depend on many factors, including growth conditions and chemical forms of P fertilizer. The increase in the efficiency of fertilizer use can be achieved by a better supply of nutrients temporally and spatially corresponding to the crop requirements and the enhanced P efficiency of wheat will contribute to reducing the use of high amounts of phosphorus fertilizers, enables sustainable agriculture on soils with low phosphorus content in arid region of Algeria.

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